

HARMONY OF MIND AND SPIRIT**Bozarqul Khudayberdiyevich Karimov***Associate Professor of “Social sciences” department at Bukhara
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Annotation: The article describes the origin of mind, its multiversity and complexity, explains multilateral i.e. ontological, gynecological, social, pedagogical and psychological approaches that are necessary’ to understand the essence of mind. Also the article enlightens the harmony of mind with spirit, first of all with the forms of sense, intellect, imagination, thinking as well as physiological and psychoanalysis principles.

Keywords: Consciousness, reflection, conditional and non-conditional reflections, a human brain, language and thinking, the using (manipulation) of consciousness in anti-humanistic or countervailing purposes.

The humanity today or tomorrow will definitely ask the question what is the purpose of its existence. This is not a simple question and to find the answer the humanity will have to look back to the history. The life of humanity is not short it is measured by the age of the Earth. The Earth and the Sun spent 4.5 billion years for the intellect to appear. This is not a short period. We are the product of a long-term natural process. It is obvious that our mind appeared as a weapon in the struggle for survival. And this exceptionally manifested mind’s property which is the ability of matter, the universe to feel itself, the ability of nature to sense itself. This is really a miracle, a phenomenon - a singular case. We can come across with different big or small miracles in life. MATERIALS AND METHODS Actually, do we understand the essence of our mind? How do we use the capabilities of our mind and intelligence? What are the mysterious, astonishing sides of mind and insanity? The intelligence is the highest form of a mental activity, it is the process of reflection of objective reality in mind. The intelligence is a weapon to understand the environment, social activities, reality as well as a fundamental prerequisite for human activities, Creative works, discoveries, inventions, suggestions are the

products of the intelligence. The role of mind and intelligence is very important in the development of society. In addition, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in his book “The highest spirituality is an unbeatable power” noted for a reason that if we compare, the, implementation of dreams inherent to human being, the required matter and spiritual factors for his intellectual existing, to wings of a bird, I think it would be reasonable.” » Due to a multiversity and complexity of mind, it is studied by many subjects and that’s why the mind is a spiritual phenomenon that cannot be described generally. The mind is only inherent for a human being that summarizes the reflection of reality by the help of speech and tongue, according to the purpose, the subjective form of the objective world that is manifested constructively und creatively. From the first years of independence human being and his life is being ascended as a superior value. In particular, studying of different sides of spiritual world of human being is becoming the actual problem nowadays. The base of this problem is connected with the subject - human mind and spirit. These problems were scientifically justified by I. P. Pavlov and I. M. Sechenov in their teachings about physiological principles of mind. I. P. Pavlov noted that habitual harmony in mind and spirit problems should not be limited only to the conditional and unconditional reflexes. In point of fact later Sigmund Freud has justified relationships of a mind and insanity in his works. Sigmund Freud noted that: “There are unperceived primitive instincts hidden in us and no any culture can protect person from their sudden manifestation; the instincts that are inherent primitive periods, that are far from ethical concepts lay in insanity. No matter how much we try to get rid of these primitive instincts we cannot escape from them completely, at least we can forward them to create cultural and ethical concepts.” The human brain plays an important role in emerging and developing of mind. Brain is a central part of human and animal nervous system; brain ensures the control of complex vital functions and environment interactions of organism. Human brain weights 1000-1400 g and consists of 14-15 billion nerve cells. If it was possible to model the nerve endings then it would be possible to make a cybernetical device equivalent to the building of Moscow State University. As you can see, phenomena exist in the past

and present. But in the near future our descendants may be listed among them. Such world famous persons like ibn Sino (Avicenna) who was able to tell the names of hundreds of herbs and which diseases could be cured with the help of them, Imom al Bukhariy who could remember thousands of hadiths, Khodja Mukhammad Porso who could remember thousands of poems, Alisher Navoi the great cultural personality, all were born in our land which is the evidence that the power to emerge the capabilities of mind had already formed in us. Through the development of humanity, opportunities for access to human consciousness technologies have widened. The valuable tips for effective use of such technologies theories have a 1st increased. The general feature of these theories is that the authors of this theory try to give a scientific justification for managing the mind, first of all, that it is necessary to transform people into a crowd, and then tried to “justify” that they can be directed to anywhere.

Their purpose is that they try to lead them to a meaningless life by misleading the minds of tins people. At the same time, they try to instill the ideology they want into people by subordinating them to themselves.

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